

Staff Survey

13 responses

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1. What is your title in " Interior design (1) " studio course?

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9 responses

2. As studio course staff member, which studio type did you experience during the pandemic phase (COVID 19)?

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11 responses

3. In comparison with the chosen studio type, based on your opinion, which studio setting was the most efficient in the quality of teaching and learning?

13 responses

4. In your interior design (1) studio course, which project do you find more effective in the quality of teaching and learning?

13 responses

5. During the **INDIVIDUAL** project, which of the *learning by doing* criteria was achieved from your point of view? (pick two only)

13 responses

6. During the **COLLABORATIVE** project, which of the *learning by doing* criteria was achieved from your point of view? (pick two only)

13 responses

7. As a staff member, what did the **COLLABORATIVE** project experience mainly achieve from the following points? (pick two only)

12 responses

8. **Potential learning** prepares students for their professional careers, which project encouraged potential learning in your opinion?

13 responses

9. Based on your previous answer, how was the **potential learning** achieved? (pick two only)

13 responses

10. There are several **technological interventions** in studio courses, regarding the taught course, which criteria was needed the most for the quality of teaching and learning? (pick two only)

13 responses

11. Based on the previous question, which project achieved the chosen *technological interventions*?

13 responses

12. An effective teaching and learning process focuses on the design process instead of the final outcome, was this *process-focused* approach achieved?

13 responses

13. Based on your previous answer, which criteria emphasize your *process-focused* answer? (pick two only)

13 responses

14. *Reflective learning* include 4 modes/phases respectively (habitual, understanding, reflection and critical reflection) to improve the student's learning skills, which phase did the majority of students reach in their **INDIVIDUAL** project?

12 responses

15. **Reflective learning** include 4 modes/phases respectively (habitual, understanding, reflection and critical reflection) to improve the student's learning skills, which phase did the majority of students reach in their **COLLABORATIVE** project?

12 responses

16. Regarding the teaching and learning experience, how much are you satisfied with the quality of education given during the **INDIVIDUAL PROJECT**?

13 responses

17. Regarding the teaching and learning experience, how much are you satisfied with the quality of education given during the **COLLABORATIVE** project?

13 responses

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